

Part 3 Biomechanics in endodontics (Article Series), Effect of the endodontic post used on the dentine, soft vs stiffer material, novel approach via numerical model, Stupid models for interpreting living organs

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Abstract

Conversion of the living dentine to dead dentine simply limits its stiffening ability. Dentine fatigue life is an overlooked subject that needs more emphasis. In this paper, we are introducing a dentine fatigue numerical model.

Keywords: Bone, Biomechanics, dental implants, ankylotic teeth, stiffness of bone, jaw weakeners, jaw stiffeners.

Introduction

Dentine is a unique material with exceptional mechanical properties. It could be defined as fibrous material stabilized by calcium inorganic content. 2 important features that stabilize the dentine fibers inside the matrix:

- The tethering of the non-organic material
- The arrangement of the collagen fibers

The arrangement of the collagen fibers is embracing in a circular fashion around the pulp, which could be regarded as a central void in the center of the tooth and is called the pulp chamber. There are tiny microscopic another voids, called dentinal tubules, that radiate from the pulp to the outer surface of the tooth, through which each hole invests a single process of the dentine building and sensing single cell odontoblasts. The pulp and dentinal tubules' inner diameter at the beginning of the tooth life is relatively large in comparison to the advanced age.

With aging, the inner diameter of the dentinal tubule will be reduced and even might be obliterated, resulting in translucent dentine, especially at the apex. The pulp chamber will also be reduced in size by deposition of secondary dentine due to the increased mechanical load demands and continuous loss of strength of the same pulp material.

In our previous paper, we demonstrated the effect of the carious lesion on the strain distribution in the framework of the tooth, resulting in possible mechanical stimulation of the pulp that orients the new dentine formation.

**Whenever there's a deformable hard tissue component and a reciprocating load, bone morphogenic proteins are present to guide the hard tissue formation process
Zainab's law and the gradient of the stiffness should be reviewed.**

Dentine is a non REMODELABLE but modifiable material. The addition of the new dentine material to the dentine will be stopped after endodontic treatment is established, resulting in the conversion of the dentine

from living material to a dead engineering material with limited fatigue life. Living dentine already contains what we could call a dead portion (no remodeling capacity), but still, the pulp could modify it. The dentine after endodontic treatment is like bone after bisphosphonate administration. In such cases, many patients had idiopathic bone fracture and the cause is that the repair of the bone is defective due to the halting of osteoclast action, the inhibition of microcrack repair, and the formation of new bone material. The stress number curvature of the dentine should be established when reviewing designs and material properties. Endodontically treated teeth need reinforcement as the structure is highly defective due to the carious lesion or at least due to the access opening to instrument the pulp chamber. Whether to choose a plastic post with fibers (glass or quartz) or choose the metallic one needs mechanical characterization to identify the performance of the 2 variants and compare it to the untreated tooth.

Methods

A generic numerical model had been used to represent part of the anatomical structure properties.

Figure 1 All models are numbers-driven.

Figure 2 These numbers could be reviewed and changed for the purpose of investigating different features.

Figure 3 The diameter of the root, post, and the thickness of the PD ligament and the cement is pparent

All our models are numbers-driven, and any changes needed are just to change these numbers. Many design features could be done based on the specific number. A generic model of a central incisor tooth had been assumed, as shown in the previous figures and submitted to the numerical simulation. 1st simulated model represented a natural tooth, the second representing tooth with a metallic post, and the third was assumed to be from a fiber post. In all models, the tooth model was embedded in a block of bone-like material.

As we are dealing with the tooth, assuming that the tooth had been restored directly, we assumed that the crown analogue is made from plastic materials.

Results and discussion

Our criteria of evaluation are that the better solution is one that respects the limited fatigue life of the dentine after endodontic treatment. The condition of the dentine after endodontic treatment is like the condition of bone after bisphosphonate administration, where an idiopathic fracture could ensue. In the case of dentine, we should manipulate the loads so that the stresses are transferred in a way that does not cause the dentine to lose its strength fast.

We should always remember that biocompatibility is a design-dependent variable

Dentine repair is initiated by 2 pathways

- Cellular driven by odontoblasts that act like a strain gauge or a load cell
- The growth factor embedded within the dentin matrix

Almost all physiological processes related to the pulp and its derivatives will be halted after endodontic treatment.

Figure 4 On the left, the natural tooth model middle the stiff post; on the right, the soft post. This is the displacement figure.

The displacement in the case of the stiff post is widely distributed, but in the case of the soft post is concentrated at narrower region with higher values.

5

Figure 5 The deformation of the root on the right, where the metal post had been used, is better, as shown by the lowered center of rotation.

Figure 6 The ratio of the maximum displacement in the crown-like structure when using any post, and the resulting displacement when using any post, should be calculated

Ratio of the maximum displacement for the roots to the maximum displacement of the crown like the following:

- $0.389/1.81$ for the soft post = 0.214
- $0.293/1.05$ for the metallic post = 0.279

That simply means the metallic post had a better ability to deform the domains in a way that prevents local bending of the dentine.

These ratios should always be seen and sought.

Figure 7 On the left, the natural tooth model middle the stiff post; on the right, the soft post. This is the strain energy density figure.

The amount of the strain energy density in the stiff post is much higher, in contrast to the soft post, where the strain energy density is higher in the tooth material when the material of the post is assigned to a softer material.

Figure 8 Post-cement interface should be evaluated carefully. The strain of this region in the case of a metallic post, could have a higher failure of debonding.

Figure 9 In contrast to the post-cement interface, the tooth dentent interface is much better when the metallic post is chosen.

The debonding could be solved easily, and the usage of screw like metal post is one of the best practical solutions to mitigate this issue.

Figure 10 A screw-like metallic post is one of the best solutions that provides mechanical integration with the cement, reducing the deboning of the posts to the greatest extent. Image provided courtesy of Dr. Sadeer Riyadh and reproduced with permission.

There is no significant room for statistics in the FEA studies as this subject is an academic spice added to the research.

Figure 11 On the left, the natural tooth model middle the stiff post; on the right, the soft post. This is the strain figure.

The strain in the tooth is continuous with the soft post, but in the case of the stiff post, its distribution is different. The lower region in the stiff post has a separated region of strain, indicating better and deeper distribution.

Figure 12 This is the second principal strain of the 3 models. Slight changes are present across the different models.

Figure 13 V Mises stress of the PD space. The higher involvement in the upper part of the PD ligament is apparent in the case of a natural tooth and the plastic soft post.

The plastic post is gaining results closer to those of the natural tooth in some results, but this should not deceive us or distract us from avoiding its usage due to the fact that the dentine is getting limited fatigue life.

Figure 14 Displacement of the PD ligament space, we had not analyzed the maximum displacement of the PD ligament space. The tooth configuration had a unique ability to transfer loads, thanks to the arrangement of the mechanical properties of the tooth itself and the investing tissues.

Figure 15 The deformation is showing the true story about the center of rotation and the resultant pattern. On the left, the softer post, and on the right, the stiffer post

Figure 16 The effect of the stiff and soft post extends to the bone. The comparison to the natural model had not been done. All numerical simulations should be compared to physical lab tests.

Conclusion

This work was to build a number-driven numerical model that shows different aspects of the effect of the stiffness on the dentine, whether using plastic or metallic posts. These numerical models could be tuned parametrically regarding mechanical properties and dimensions. Many aspects of the mechanical performance clearly go in favor of the selection of the metallic posts' implementation in the rehabilitation of the endodontically treated teeth.

References

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Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, largest secondary referral center in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.